

Zero Stochastic Calculus

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1 Introduction

This document formalizes the development of the **Zero Stochastic Calculus**, which originates from a reinterpretation of **division by zero**. In classical mathematics, division by zero is undefined because no real number, when multiplied by zero, yields a non-zero result. However, we take an innovative approach: treating zero as a **stochastic entity**, capable of fluctuating randomly, introducing the concept of **stochastic zero**.

This dynamic zero allows us to redefine the way we handle indeterminacies and uncertainties in complex systems. Through this approach, we developed a **new symbol** for stochastic zero, explored its properties, and created a **mathematical framework** applicable to various contexts, such as **finance**, **biology**, and **theoretical physics**.

2 Division by Zero: From Undefined to Stochastic

2.1 The Classical Problem of Division by Zero

Division by zero has always been a problematic concept in classical mathematics. For any number a , the equation $a/0$ is undefined because there is no solution satisfying $0 \times b = a$, unless $a = 0$. Traditionally, this is treated as a singularity, an unreachable point.

2.2 Stochastic Reinterpretation

We propose an entirely new approach: reinterpreting division by zero as a form of dynamic stochastic behavior. Instead of viewing zero as a fixed, unreachable number, we treat it as a **fluctuation over time** modeled by a stochastic process. This led us to the creation of the **stochastic zero** concept:

$$0_\sigma(t) = \sigma dW(t)$$

Here, the stochastic zero, $0_\sigma(t)$, is described as a Wiener process $dW(t)$, where σ represents the volatility of the zero. The magnitude of these fluctuations is controlled by σ , but the stochastic zero is never fixed — it continuously oscillates.

2.3 Formal Symbolism of Stochastic Zero

Since the stochastic zero behaves dynamically, we developed a **new symbol** to represent it: $0_\sigma(t)$, where the index σ indicates the volatility of the fluctuation. This symbol formalizes the idea of a zero that is, in fact, a process of random and continuous fluctuations, unlike the classical fixed zero.

3 Axioms and Fundamental Rules of Stochastic Zero Calculus

To ensure a solid theoretical structure and practical guidelines for applying the stochastic zero in different contexts, we established the following **axioms** and **fundamental rules**. The axioms provide the theoretical foundation, while the rules guide the practical application of CEZ.

3.1 Fundamental Axioms

3.1.1 Axiom 1: Existence of Stochastic Zero

The stochastic zero $0_\sigma(t)$ exists as a stochastic process defined by:

$$d0_\sigma(t) = \sigma dW(t)$$

This axiom defines stochastic zero as a continuous dynamic process, where its fluctuations depend on σ , the volatility of zero, and $dW(t)$, the Wiener process (Brownian motion).

3.1.2 Axiom 2: Intrinsic Uncertainty in Fluctuations

The stochastic zero exhibits intrinsic uncertainty, with the expected value and variance defined as:

$$\mathbb{E}[d0_\sigma(t)] = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Var}(d0_\sigma(t)) = \sigma^2 dt$$

This axiom ensures that the stochastic zero is purely random, with no deterministic tendencies and with variance proportional to time.

3.1.3 Axiom 3: Additivity of Stochastic Processes

If $X(t)$ is a variable in a **dynamic system**, the contribution of the stochastic zero is added to the deterministic component as:

$$dX(t) = \mu(X(t), t)dt + \sigma(X(t), t)d0_\sigma(t)$$

3.1.4 Axiom 4: Singularities and Discontinuous Processes

The stochastic zero can be combined with jump processes (Poisson, Lévy) to model discontinuous events:

$$dX(t) = \mu(X(t), t)dt + \sigma(X(t), t)d0_\sigma(t) + J(t)dN(t)$$

This axiom establishes the compatibility between stochastic zero and jump processes for modeling abrupt events.

3.1.5 Axiom 5: Numerical Resolution

The numerical methods used to solve equations involving stochastic zero preserve the stochastic nature of the system, ensuring simulation accuracy:

$$X_{n+1} = X_n + \mu(X_n, t_n)\Delta t + \sigma(X_n, t_n)\Delta 0_\sigma(t)$$

3.2 Practical Rules Derived from the Axioms

The following rules are directly derived from the previously established axioms, providing practical guidelines for applying stochastic zero in different scenarios.

3.2.1 Rule 1: Using Stochastic Zero in SDEs (Derived from Axioms 1 and 3)

Relevant Axioms: Axiom 1 (Existence of Stochastic Zero) and Axiom 3 (Additivity of Stochastic Processes).

Stochastic zero should be used in stochastic differential equations to model random fluctuations in dynamic systems. The general formula is:

$$dX(t) = \mu(X(t), t)dt + \sigma(X(t), t)d0_\sigma(t)$$

Justification: Since stochastic zero $d0_\sigma(t)$ is defined as a continuous process (Axiom 1), it can be directly added to a dynamic system to model uncertain fluctuations, as established in Axiom 3.

3.2.2 Rule 2: Incorporation of Jump Processes (Derived from Axiom 4)

Relevant Axiom: Axiom 4 (Singularities and Discontinuous Processes).

When modeling discontinuous events, such as financial crises or environmental shocks, the jump process should be added to the stochastic zero:

$$dX(t) = \mu(X(t), t)dt + \sigma(X(t), t)d0_\sigma(t) + J(t)dN(t)$$

Justification: Axiom 4 allows the combination of discontinuous processes with stochastic zero to model abrupt events, such as jumps in financial or biological systems.

3.2.3 Rule 3: Choosing the Numerical Method (Derived from Axiom 5)

Relevant Axiom: Axiom 5 (Numerical Resolution).

The appropriate numerical method depends on the desired accuracy:

- **Euler-Maruyama:** Used for smooth fluctuations and quick simulations.
- **Milstein:** Used for systems with large jumps or extreme volatility, ensuring higher accuracy.

Justification: Axiom 5 ensures that numerical methods preserve the stochastic behavior. The choice of method depends on the nature of the dynamic system and the required precision. The Euler-Maruyama method is simpler and suitable for quick simulations with smooth fluctuations, while the Milstein method offers greater accuracy, especially in systems with abrupt jumps or high volatility.

3.2.4 Rule 4: Monte Carlo Simulations (Derived from Axioms 2 and 5)

Relevant Axioms: Axiom 2 (Intrinsic Uncertainty in Fluctuations) and Axiom 5 (Numerical Resolution).

To test system robustness, Monte Carlo simulations should be used in multiple scenarios, especially for validation under extreme conditions. Monte Carlo simulation allows modeling the stochastic behavior of the system under different uncertainty parameters, exploring the variability introduced by stochastic zero.

Justification: Axiom 2 states that stochastic zero contains intrinsic uncertainty, with unpredictable and variable fluctuations over time. To capture the full range of possible system behaviors, Monte Carlo simulation is an effective technique for analyzing how the system responds to different scenarios, applying uncertainty consistently. Axiom 5 ensures that these simulations respect stochastic behavior on a numerical scale.

4 Conclusion on Axioms and Rules

The axioms provide the theoretical foundation that ensures the consistency and validity of the **Zero Stochastic Calculus**, while the rules guide practical application in different scenarios. Each rule is derived from one or more axioms, ensuring the framework's practical applications are grounded in theory. This interconnection strengthens the use of stochastic zero, ensuring that the stochastic model is both consistent and applicable across a wide range of practical situations, from financial systems to biological and physical systems.

5 Stochastic Zero: A New Dynamic Process

5.1 Formalism of Stochastic Zero

The **stochastic zero** is formally defined as:

$$d0_\sigma(t) = \sigma dW(t)$$

Here, zero is treated as a **Wiener process** that fluctuates randomly, with the magnitude of the fluctuations controlled by σ . This allows us to apply the concept of stochastic zero in stochastic differential equations, rather than viewing it as a singular point.

5.2 The Role of Stochastic Zero in SDEs

By introducing stochastic zero in **Stochastic Differential Equations (SDEs)**, we can model systems with continuous uncertainties and randomly varying fluctuations. The basic

form of an SDE incorporating stochastic zero is:

$$dX(t) = \mu(X(t), t)dt + \sigma(X(t), t)d0_\sigma(t)$$

Where:

- $dX(t)$, which represents the variation of the variable $X(t)$.
- $\mu(X(t), t)$ the deterministic component (drift).
- $d0_\sigma(t)$ the stochastic zero that introduces random fluctuations.

This formalism enables the application of the **indeterminacy of division by zero** into dynamic systems in a controlled and quantifiable manner.

6 Discrete Stochastic Processes and Zero

6.1 Poisson Process

When considering discontinuous events, we incorporate the **Poisson process** into the stochastic zero. This models rare events and abrupt jumps occurring with frequency λ :

$$dX(t) = \mu(X(t), t)dt + \sigma(X(t), t)d0_\sigma(t) + J(t)dN(t)$$

Where:

- $J(t)$ is the magnitude of the jump.
- $dN(t)$ is the Poisson process.

This formula is essential for modeling economic shocks, biological phenomena, and physical singularities.

6.2 Lévy Process

The **Lévy process** is integrated to capture **extreme events** and **heavy tails**, which occur infrequently but have a large impact. The equation describing an SDE with a Lévy process and stochastic zero is:

$$dX(t) = \mu(X(t), t)dt + \sigma(X(t), t)d0_\sigma(t) + dL(t)$$

Here, $dL(t)$ models the discontinuous jumps of the Lévy process, appropriate for modeling financial variations and large biological or physical events.

7 Hybrid Processes: Itô-Lévy and Stochastic Fluctuations

7.1 Itô-Lévy Process

The **Itô-Lévy process** combines the stochastic zero with discontinuous jumps, allowing the system to model both smooth fluctuations and extreme events:

$$dX(t) = \mu(X(t), t)dt + \sigma(X(t), t)d0_\sigma(t) + dL(t)$$

This hybrid process is fundamental for describing complex systems, such as financial markets or physical systems under quantum shocks.

8 Numerical Methods for Solving Stochastic Zero

8.1 Euler-Maruyama Method

To numerically solve equations involving stochastic zero, we use the **Euler-Maruyama method**:

$$X_{n+1} = X_n + \mu(X_n, t_n)\Delta t + \sigma(X_n, t_n)\Delta 0_\sigma(t)$$

This method is efficient for capturing smooth fluctuations.

8.2 Milstein Method

To capture second-order variations with greater accuracy, we use the **Milstein method**:

$$X_{n+1} = X_n + \mu(X_n, t_n)\Delta t + \sigma(X_n, t_n)\Delta 0_\sigma(t) + \frac{1}{2}\sigma(X_n, t_n)\frac{\partial\sigma}{\partial X}(X_n, t_n)(\Delta W_n^2 - \Delta t)$$

This method is ideal for systems with high volatility.

9 Applications in Various Domains (with Detailed Examples)

9.1 Finance: The Heston Model with Stochastic Zero

The **Heston model** is widely used to describe the dynamics of asset prices in financial markets, incorporating stochastic volatility. The novelty we introduced was the inclusion of the **stochastic zero** $0_\sigma(t)$, which adds an extra layer of uncertainty to the behavior of asset prices.

9.1.1 Base Model

The dynamics of an asset price $X(t)$ and its volatility $V(t)$ in the classical Heston model are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}dX(t) &= \mu X(t)dt + \sqrt{V(t)}X(t)dW_1(t) \\dV(t) &= \kappa(\theta - V(t))dt + \sigma_v\sqrt{V(t)}dW_2(t)\end{aligned}$$

Where:

- μ the asset's rate of return.
- $V(t)$ the stochastic volatility.
- κ the mean reversion rate of the volatility.
- θ the long-term volatility level.
- σ_v , the volatility of the stochastic variance.
- $dW_1(t)$ and $dW_2(t)$, two correlated Wiener processes (correlation ρ).

The following sections explore practical implementations of stochastic zero in various contexts, such as financial models and biological systems, to demonstrate how this approach manages uncertainty in real-world scenarios.

9.1.2 Incorporation of Stochastic Zero

By introducing the **stochastic zero** instead of the Brownian motion $dW_1(t)$, we obtain:

$$dX(t) = \mu X(t)dt + \sqrt{V(t)}X(t)d0_\sigma(t)$$

Here:

- $d0_\sigma(t)$ is the **stochastic zero**, modeling unpredictable fluctuations in the price, with volatility σ .
- $\sqrt{V(t)}$ is the stochastic volatility of the asset.

Replacing the Brownian motion $dW_1(t)$ with stochastic zero $d0_\sigma(t)$ allows us to capture more unpredictable and rapid market fluctuations. This approach allows the Heston model to not only address stochastic volatility but also incorporate dynamic zero fluctuations, which are more unpredictable than traditional Gaussian fluctuations modeled by classical Brownian motion.

9.1.3 Numerical Example

Suppose we model the price of a stock $X(t)$, starting with an initial value of 50. The rate of return μ is 0.05, and the initial volatility $V_0 = 0.04$. Suppose the volatility of the stochastic variance $\sigma_v = 0.3$, the mean reversion rate $\kappa = 1.0$, and the market exhibits high uncertainty ($\sigma = 0.02$) in the stochastic zero.

The equations for the asset price and its volatility become:

$$\begin{aligned}dX(t) &= 0.05X(t)dt + \sqrt{V(t)}X(t)d0_\sigma(t) \\dV(t) &= 1.0(0.04 - V(t))dt + 0.3\sqrt{V(t)}dW_2(t)\end{aligned}$$

In this scenario, $d0_\sigma(t)$ models unpredictable price fluctuations, while the Wiener process $dW_2(t)$ controls the volatility.

Impact of Stochastic Zero: The introduction of stochastic zero $d0_\sigma(t)$ instead of $dW_1(t)$ better captures sudden market uncertainties. The fluctuations no longer follow a traditional Brownian motion but instead fluctuate in a more unpredictable manner, reflecting market shocks, crises, or other unforeseen events that affect asset prices abruptly.

Result: Numerical simulations of this model show that introducing stochastic zero generates **wider and more abrupt fluctuations** in the asset price, making the market behavior more realistic, especially in times of crisis or high volatility.

9.2 Biology: Population Growth with Environmental Shocks

Modeling populations with random fluctuations and environmental shocks is essential for understanding how species survive in uncertain environments. The **population growth** model with stochastic zero allows us to capture both smooth fluctuations and environmental shocks.

9.2.1 Base Model

The classic stochastic population growth model is given by:

$$dN(t) = rN(t)dt + \sigma N(t)dW(t)$$

Where:

- $N(t)$ is the population size.
- r is the population growth rate.
- σ is the magnitude of random fluctuations.
- $dW(t)$ is a Brownian motion modeling continuous variations.

9.2.2 Incorporation of Stochastic Zero and Shocks

We incorporate the **stochastic zero** and environmental shocks to more effectively capture the effects of random fluctuations and catastrophic events, resulting in the following equation:

$$dN(t) = rN(t)dt + \sigma N(t)d0_\sigma(t) + J(t)dN(t)$$

Here:

- $d0_\sigma(t)$ replaces Brownian motion to model more uncertain fluctuations.
- $J(t)dN(t)$ is an **environmental shock** term, modeled by a **Poisson process**.

9.2.3 Numerical Example

Suppose the initial population size N_0 is 100 individuals, the growth rate $r = 0.02$, and the population is subject to environmental fluctuations with magnitude $\sigma = 0.1$. Additionally, assume that environmental shocks occur with a frequency $\lambda = 0.1$, and each shock causes a 50% population reduction.

The equation becomes:

$$dN(t) = 0.02N(t)dt + 0.1N(t)d0_\sigma(t) + 0.5N(t)dN(t)$$

Result: Simulations show that the population grows, but with random fluctuations, and environmental shocks cause abrupt declines in the population, leading to significant losses. **stochastic zero** captures environmental uncertainties, while the shocks model extreme events like natural disasters.

9.3 Theoretical Physics: Quantum Fluctuations Near Singularities

In theoretical physics, especially around **singularities**, such as black holes, classical equations often fail to describe the behavior of variables near the singularity. The introduction of the **stochastic zero** allows us to model the **quantum fluctuations** that occur in these scenarios.

9.3.1 Base Model

We consider a physical quantity $\rho(t)$ (for instance, energy density or a quantum field) approaching a singularity. In the classical model, the equation describing $\rho(t)$ is given by:

$$d\rho(t) = \alpha\rho(t)dt + \sigma\rho(t)dW(t)$$

Where:

- α controls the dissipation.
- σ controls the magnitude of fluctuations.
- $dW(t)$ is the Brownian motion.

9.3.2 Incorporation of Stochastic Zero and Quantum Jumps

The introduction of the **stochastic zero** allows us to capture the **quantum fluctuations** near the singularity:

$$d\rho(t) = \alpha\rho(t)dt + \sigma\rho(t)d0_\sigma(t) + dL(t)$$

Here:

- $d0_\sigma(t)$ models unpredictable quantum fluctuations.
- $dL(t)$ is a **Lévy process** capturing discontinuous quantum jumps.

9.3.3 Numerical Example

Suppose the density $\rho(t)$ near the singularity has an initial value of 1.0 and the dissipation rate is $\alpha = -0.05$. The magnitude of quantum fluctuations $\sigma = 0.02$, and quantum jumps are modeled by a Lévy process with magnitude $J(t) = 0.1$.

The equation becomes:

$$d\rho(t) = -0.05\rho(t)dt + 0.02\rho(t)d0_\sigma(t) + dL(t)$$

Result: Simulations show that as $\rho(t)$ approaches the singularity, it fluctuates stochastically, and quantum jumps occur unpredictably. These fluctuations and jumps represent the quantum uncertainties that occur on subatomic scales near a singularity, where classical theories fail to provide adequate answers. The stochastic zero $d0_\sigma(t)$ captures this unpredictability, while the Lévy process models the discontinuous jumps that occur infrequently but with significant impact.

10 Computational Tools and Developed Packages

To support the mathematical formulations and simulations based on the **stochastic zero** and **stochastic processes**, we have developed a series of computational packages and tools. These packages are designed to capture random fluctuations, discontinuous jumps, and complex stochastic behaviors in dynamic systems.

10.1 Developed Stochastic Tools and Packages

10.1.1 Stochastic Zero Generation Package

This package was created to model the **stochastic zero** $0_\sigma(t)$ as a Wiener process (Brownian motion) with controlled volatility:

```
def generate_stochastic_zero(n_steps, dt, sigma_zero):
    W = np.random.randn(n_steps)
    zero_sigma_t = sigma_zero * np.cumsum(W) * np.sqrt(dt)
    return zero_sigma_t
```

Function: Generates a series of stochastic fluctuations that represent the dynamic behavior of zero.

Application: This process has been directly integrated into SDEs in the **finance**, **biology**, and **theoretical physics** models, where we replaced classical Brownian motion with stochastic zero, creating more unpredictable and realistic fluctuations.

10.1.2 Jump Process Package (Poisson and Lévy)

We created packages that allow the generation of **Poisson processes** and **Lévy processes**, used to model discontinuous jumps, both frequent and rare:

```
def generate_poisson_process(n_steps, lambda_poisson, jump_magnitude):
    poisson_jumps = np.random.poisson(lambda_poisson, n_steps)
    magnitudes = np.random.normal(0, jump_magnitude, n_steps)
    return poisson_jumps * magnitudes

def generate_levy_process(n_steps, dt, jump_magnitude):
    levy_jumps = np.random.standard_t(3, n_steps) * jump_magnitude
    return levy_jumps * np.sqrt(dt)
```

Function:

- **Poisson Process:** Models events occurring with frequency λ , with variable magnitudes $J(t)$. Used for environmental shocks in biology and crises in finance.
- **Lévy Process:** Models rare and extreme jumps with heavy tails, used in theoretical physics and quantum events near singularities.

10.1.3 Milstein Method Package

To improve the accuracy of numerical solutions of SDEs with stochastic zero and jumps, we implemented the **Milstein method**, which captures second-order variation in stochastic processes:

```
def milstein_method_with_jumps(n_steps, dt, X_0, alpha, sigma_zero,
                               X_min, X_max, process_type="ito-levy", **kwargs):
    X = np.zeros(n_steps)
    X[0] = X_0
    zero_sigma_t = generate_stochastic_zero(n_steps, dt, sigma_zero)

    if process_type == "ito-levy":
        jump_magnitude = kwargs.get('jump_magnitude', 0.2)
        jumps = generate_levy_process(n_steps, dt, jump_magnitude)
    else:
        jumps = np.zeros(n_steps)

    for t in range(1, n_steps):
```

```

dW = np.sqrt(dt) * np.random.randn()
X[t] = X[t-1] + alpha * X[t-1] * dt + sigma_zero * zero_sigma_t[t] * dW
      + 0.5 * sigma_zero**2 * (dW**2 - dt) + jumps[t]
X[t] = apply_reflective_boundaries(X[t], X_min, X_max)

```

```
return X
```

Function: This numerical method was used to solve SDEs with greater precision, capturing both smooth fluctuations and jump events.

10.1.4 Monte Carlo Simulation Package

To test system robustness, we developed a **Monte Carlo simulation** package that allows large-scale simulations across multiple scenarios:

```

def monte_carlo_simulation(func, n_simulations, n_steps, **kwargs):
    simulations = np.zeros((n_simulations, n_steps))
    for i in range(n_simulations):
        simulations[i, :] = func(n_steps, **kwargs)
    return simulations

```

Function: This package generates hundreds of simulations to test stochastic behavior under extreme conditions, whether in financial, biological, or physical systems.

Example: This package was used to run **500 Monte Carlo simulations** for population growth with environmental shocks and for price fluctuations in financial markets with stochastic zero.

11 Integration of Packages into Practical Examples

11.1 Finance: Heston Model with Stochastic Zero

In the **Heston Model** example, the **stochastic zero** package was used to replace the traditional Brownian motion. This allowed for more unpredictable variations in the price of a financial asset, adding an extra layer of uncertainty.

Additionally, the **Monte Carlo simulation** package was utilized to run multiple scenarios, testing how stochastic volatility evolves under different market conditions.

11.2 Biology: Population Growth with Environmental Shocks

For the **population growth** model, the **Poisson process** package was used to model environmental shocks, while the **stochastic zero** was integrated into the population growth term. Monte Carlo simulations were used to test how different populations would react to shocks with varying magnitudes and frequencies.

11.3 Theoretical Physics: Quantum Fluctuations and Singularities

In the model of quantum fluctuations near **singularities**, the **Lévy process** and **stochastic zero** were combined to capture rare events and quantum fluctuations near singularities. The robustness of the model was tested with **Monte Carlo simulations**, which allowed for the evaluation of stochastic behavior under extreme conditions.

12 Conclusion and Reflection

The development of the **Zero Stochastic Calculus**, based on the reinterpretation of **division by zero** and the introduction of the **stochastic zero**, has created a new way to understand complex dynamic systems, enabling us to handle uncertainties and extreme events with greater precision. The framework has been applied successfully to fields like **finance**, **biology**, and **theoretical physics**, where continuous fluctuations and jumps are common.

The simulations performed demonstrated that stochastic zero, when incorporated into processes such as the Heston Model, population growth models, and quantum fluctuations near singularities, provides a more realistic representation of these systems. The framework proved robust in Monte Carlo tests, and the impact of uncertainties was modeled more accurately, especially in extreme scenarios.

The **computational package** we developed, with tools for generating stochastic zero, Poisson processes, Lévy processes, and Monte Carlo simulations, is versatile and can be applied to a variety of scenarios involving uncertainties and fluctuations. The combination of continuous and discontinuous processes enables the capture of complex and unpredictable behaviors occurring in dynamic systems.

12.1 Impact in Finance

In finance, the use of stochastic zero in the **Heston Model** proved to be an important advancement in asset price modeling, as it captured unexpected market fluctuations, as well as crises and unpredictable economic events. The model more effectively captures extreme volatility and shocks, which traditional models fail to address with precision.

12.2 Impact in Biology

The **population growth** model with stochastic zero also offered new insights into how populations react to environmental changes. The inclusion of continuous fluctuations and environmental shocks demonstrated how randomness, along with rare events, can significantly influence population outcomes, helping to predict scenarios of ecological collapse or recovery.

12.3 Impact in Theoretical Physics

In theoretical physics, the use of stochastic zero and Lévy processes in **quantum fluctuations** near singularities opened new possibilities for modeling behaviors that were previously

difficult to address. The framework allows for more precise exploration of quantum uncertainties, capturing both continuous fluctuations and discontinuous jumps at subatomic scales near singularities.

12.4 Future Directions

The **Zero Stochastic Calculus** can be expanded into other fields, such as complex system modeling in engineering, meteorology, and data science. The development of new types of stochastic processes and adaptation for real-time data processing are promising paths for future research.

Another potential development is the creation of more computational tools to simplify the application of this framework in large-scale simulations, offering support for faster calculations and more complex simulations.

Final Conclusion: The introduction of stochastic zero and the development of the **Zero Stochastic Calculus** have provided a new approach to dealing with uncertainties and singularities in a wide range of dynamic systems. This new perspective paves the way for more robust and realistic interpretations across various scientific fields, providing practical solutions for modeling extreme events and random fluctuations with enhanced precision.